

Study of UsG Guided Popliteal Nerve Block for Ankle and Foot SurgeriesPranjal Dave¹, Pauravi T. Bhatt², Parth Patel³, Urvisha Tarpara⁴¹Third Year Resident Doctor, Department of Anaesthesiology, SMT. NHL Municipal Medical College, SVP hospital, Ahmedabad²Associate Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology, SMT. NHL Municipal Medical College, SVP Hospital, Ahmedabad³Managing Director, Alpha Associates, Ahmedabad⁴Senior Resident, Department of Anaesthesiology, SMT. NHL Municipal Medical College, SVP hospital, Ahmedabad

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Abstract:

Background: Popliteal Nerve Block, a form of regional anaesthesia is given for a variety of foot & ankle surgeries. It is a popular technique to decrease postoperative pain, decrease narcotic use & increase patient satisfaction. Popliteal blocks can be utilized as the sole source of anaesthesia for foot & ankle surgeries. This technique is beneficial in medically compromised patients. Profound analgesia during both the operative & post-operative time periods & avoidance of systemic complications like nausea & vomiting are also potential benefits of popliteal nerve block. Use of ultrasound allows real time visualisation of deposition of local anaesthetic and so can improve the chance of successful nerve blockade. Ultrasound also allowed dose reduction of the local anaesthetic. It reduces the number of needle passes and shortens the block onset time.

Methods: All the patients enrolled for USG guided Popliteal Nerve Block will undergo a thorough pre-anaesthetic check-up. Local parts will be examined and written informed consent will be taken from all patients. AS will be explained in detail on the night before the surgery. Patient will be advised to keep Nil per orally for at least 6 hours pre operatively. A peripheral line will be secured for all the patients. Monitors will be applied for -ECG, NIBP, SpO₂. Ultrasound machine and its probe will be properly cleaned and aseptically prepared After preparing the parts with povidone iodine, spirit and normal saline solutions, proper draping will be done and a high frequency (5-12 Hz) linear ultrasound probe will be placed transversely at the mid-popliteal crease. After localizing the popliteal artery, probe will be moved proximally to locate the sciatic nerve at or prior to its bifurcation into the tibial and common peroneal branches, the patient will be informed and then a 23G spinal (Quincke) needle will be inserted in-line with and parallel to the transducer from the lateral side of the fossa by using In-plane approach, the whole shaft will be visualized as it progresses towards the nerve. Once placement is confirmed, injection Lignocaine 1.5% 10 ml and injection Bupivacaine 0.5% 5 ml will be injected circumferentially around the sciatic nerve after negative aspiration for blood. 1. Patient will be turned into a supine position. Sensory block will be assessed by pin prick sensation (using the Hollmen scale) and motor block will be assessed by movement of fingers and the ankle joint (using the Hollmen scale).

Results: No side effects or adverse reactions were observed whatsoever. All the patients graded the experience as being very satisfied with the anaesthetic technique.

Conclusion: Ultrasound-guided popliteal fossa nerve block is an effective and successful technique to provide perioperative sensory and motor blockade for patients undergoing various foot and ankle surgeries. Complications associated with spinal epidural and general anaesthesia can be avoided. Combinations of Lignocaine and Bupivacaine as a local anaesthetic provide faster onset with virtue of good postoperative analgesia.

Keywords: Lower limb surgery, popliteal block, Ultrasound guidance, Bupivacaine, Lignocaine.

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Introduction

Regional anesthesia for foot and ankle surgery has been used extensively by podiatric surgeons for over thirty years. Regional anesthesia is ideal for ambulatory-type surgery, especially when combined with sub-hypnotic doses of sedatives to allay patient anxiety. The few disadvantages include the

need for patient education and cooperation, time to institute the block(s), patient anxiety, and the effort necessary to acquire the skills. However, the advantages far outweigh the disadvantages. There are less risks with regional anesthesia when compared to general, spinal or caudal anesthesia. Fewer drugs

with potential adverse effects are necessary especially opioids.

Popliteal blocks can potentially be utilized as the sole source of anesthesia for foot and ankle surgery. This can be beneficial in medically compromised patients. Profound analgesia during both the operative and post-operative time periods and the avoidance of systemic complications such as nausea and vomiting are also potential benefits of the popliteal nerve block.

There are several approaches to administering a popliteal sciatic nerve block, all with unique advantages and disadvantages. Commonly, a posterior approach is employed with the patient positioned prone.

Alternatively, the lateral approach can be used with patient in the supine position. The medial approach has been described in the literature, although it is less frequently utilized. There are various techniques when administering anesthetic to the therapeutic plexus of nerves of the popliteal fossa. Single and double injection, continuous infusion and bolus dosing through a perineural catheter, and the use of electrical stimulation with or without ultrasound guidance have all been described.

Materials and Methods

Ultrasound guidance shortens the block performance time, reduces the number of needle passes and shortens the block onset time. Ultrasound also allowed dose reduction of the local anaesthetic (LA). Ultrasound guidance can minimize the risk and increase the success rate to almost 100%.

The present study was conducted in 40 patients aged between 20-80 years and weighted between 40-90 kgs having ASA grades I, II and III, who underwent elective ankle and foot surgeries with expected duration between 30 minutes to 2 hours.

Pre-anaesthetic assessment: All the patients underwent a thorough pre anaesthetic checkup which included detailed history, general and physical examinations, laboratory and radiological investigations. Local part was examined and the anaesthetic plan was discussed.

VAS was explained on the night before the surgery. Informed written consent was taken from the patients and their close relatives. All patients were advised nil by mouth as per fasting guidelines.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients with known bleeding disorders.
- ASA physical status more than III.
- Pregnant women.
- Morbidly obese patients.
- Patients with local site infections.
- Mentally handicapped patients.
- Patient refused to enroll in the study.

Preparation:

On the arrival in the operation theatre, all the standard monitors (heart rate, non-invasive blood pressure, electrocardiogram and pulse-oximetry) were attached to the patient and baseline vitals were noted. A Peripheral venous line was secured with 20G intravenous cannula and intravenous fluid started. Injection glycopyrrolate 0.2 mg IV was given.

Equipment's prepared:

A portable sterile tray containing:

- Disposable syringes of 10 ml.
- Disposable 23G spinal (Quincke) needle.
- Bowls containing povidone iodine, spirit and normal saline solutions.
- Sponge holding forceps.
- Sterile gauze pieces.
- Sterile towel and towel clip.

Resuscitation equipment's including the anaesthesia delivery system, oxygen supply, various sizes of face masks, working laryngoscopes, oral and nasal airways of different sizes, laryngeal mask airways, endotracheal and tracheostomy tubes, suction apparatus, intravenous cannula of various sizes, defibrillator, emergency drugs tray.

Ultrasound machine and its probe properly cleaned and aseptically prepared for the procedure.

Position: Patient was positioned prone with head turned to the opposite side and hands kept by the side of the body. The ultrasound machine was placed on the opposite side of the lower limb that has to be anaesthetized.

Landmarks: Anatomical landmarks were identified and marked with a skin marker which included the course of the semitendinosus tendon and the biceps femoris tendon. The mid popliteal crease was identified and marked.

Procedure: After preparing the parts with povidone iodine, spirit and normal saline solutions, proper draping was done and a high frequency (5-12 Hz) ultrasound probe was placed transversely at the mid popliteal crease. After localizing the popliteal artery probe was moved proximally to locate the sciatic nerve at or prior to its bifurcation into the tibial and common peroneal branches. After identifying the sciatic nerve on ultrasound, patient was informed and then a 23G spinal (Quincke) needle was inserted in-line with and parallel to the transducer from the lateral side of the fossa by using In-plane approach. The needle traverses the plane of ultrasound and the whole shaft was visualized as it progressed towards the nerve. Once placement was confirmed by questioning the patient verbally regarding the presence of paraesthesia in the foot and ankle region, injection Lignocaine 1.5% 10 ml and

injection Bupivacaine 0.5% 10 ml was injected circumferentially around the sciatic nerve after frequent negative aspiration for blood. Patient was turned into a supine position. Sensory block was assessed by pin prick sensation (using the Hollmen scale) 40 and motor block was assessed by movement of fingers and the ankle joint (using the Hollmen scale). After confirmation of complete sensory and motor blockade, surgery was allowed

to start. Monitoring of all vitals were carried out and all the data was entered into a spreadsheet program. Time taken for sensory and motor blockade to recede completely was noted and also was the time taken till the onset of pain post-operatively. Any Intraoperative and Postoperative complications were treated accordingly and patient satisfaction was also noted. Below are reference diagrams illustrating the same.

Figure 1: showing popliteal crease and position of linear ultrasound probe

Figure 2: BF: bicepsfemoris. ST, SM: semimembranosus, semitendinosus

Figure 3: showing in-plane technique to block the sciatic nerve in popliteal fossa by using linear ultrasound probe

Figure 4: Figure shows the sciatic nerve (arrowheads) in the popliteal fossa before it divides

Figure 5: Figure shows the shaft of the spinal needle long axis in-plane technique

Figure 6: Injection of anaesthetic agent was confirmed by visualization

Figure 7: Stars showing deposition of local anaesthetic agents (circumferential around the sciatic nerve)

Following parameters were noted:

1. Time taken to execute the nerve block.
2. Time taken to achieve complete sensory and motor blockade.
3. Duration of complete sensory and motor blockade (intra-operative and post-operative).
4. Need of supplementary sedation/general anaesthesia.
5. Onset of pain for the first time in post-operative periods.
6. Intra-operative and post-operative complications.
7. Patient satisfaction.

Evaluation of sensory block (hollmen scale):

1. Normal pin prick sensation
2. Hypoalgesia (in prick sensation felt as sharp pointed but weaker compared with same area in the upper limb)
3. Analgesia (pin prick sensation perceived as touch with blunt object)
4. Anaesthesia (Complete loss of pin prick sensation)

Evaluation of motor block (hollmen scale):

1. Normal movement (the patient can move against resistance and gravity)
2. Decreased movement (decreased strength com-

- pared to opposite site)
3. Paresis (the patient can move against gravity, but not against resistance)
4. Paralysis (no movement)

After completion of surgery, the patient was shifted to a post-operative ward and watched for the duration of sensory and motor blockade periodically. Vitals were also recorded. When the sensory and motor regression was started, VAS was evaluated at a frequent interval. When VAS was greater than 4, rescue analgesia in the form of Injection Tramadol 1 mg/kg IV was slowly given. Time to rescue analgesia was noted. Patients were further managed conventionally according to the department protocol.

Statistical Analysis

All the data was entered in a spreadsheet program and statistical analysis was done by using SPSS version 20.0. Descriptive statistics were used to find frequencies, Mean and Standard deviation.

Observations and Results

Our study consisted of 40 patients, with ages ranging from 20 to 80 years and weight ranging from 40 to 90 kilograms as illustrated below. The Mean Time Taken To Achieve Complete Sensory Block Was 12.60 ± 1.37 Minutes.

Figure 8: Showing Time Taken To Achieve Complete Sensory Blockade Variation

The Mean Time Taken To Achieve Complete Motor Block Was 15.65±1.46 Minutes.

Figure 9: Showing Time Taken To Achieve Complete Motor Blockade Variation

Figure 10: Showing Hr Variation (Baseline to Post-OP)

Figure 11: Showing Systolic BP Variation (Baseline to Post-OP)

Figure 12: Showing Diastolic BP Variation (Baseline to Post-Op)

As illustrated above the haemodynamic parameters of patients remained stable and apart from the rise in HR, SBP and DBP at 5 minutes, which may be attributable to the anxiety response caused by the needle prick during the procedure, they remained close to baseline values throughout the operation.

There were no significant changes in the level of oxygen saturation during baseline, intra-op and post-op periods. The Mean Time for Duration of Surgery Was 54.03 ± 14.64 Minutes. The Mean Time for Complete Motor Blockade Was 250.00 ± 14.85 Minutes.

Figure 13: Showing Duration of Complete Motor Blockade (Intra-Op and Post-Op) Variation

The Mean Time for Complete Sensory Blockade Was 309.00±19.59 Minutes.

Figure 14: Showing Duration of Complete Sensory Blockade (Intra-Op and Post-Op) Variation

Table 1: Showing Patient Satisfaction Level

Satisfaction Level	No. Of Patients
Very satisfied	39
Not satisfied	01
Total	40

Except One, All The Patients Were Very Satisfied In Our Study.

Table 2: Showing Mean Time of Various Parameters in Our Study

Mean Time taken to	Minutes
Execute the block	4.80±1.32
To achieve sensory blockade	12.60±1.37
To achieve motor blockade	15.65±1.46
Duration of operation	54.03±14.64
Duration of complete motor blockade	250.00±14.85
Duration of complete sensory blockade	309.00±19.59
Onset of postoperative pain	336.50±17.33

Complications (If Any): Any complications related to drugs and procedure, haemodynamic and neurological complications were not seen in our study.

- One patient had rigors and other patient had irrelevant talking (h/o psychiatric illness) for which no pharmacological interventions were required.
- One case of a diabetic foot debridement was considered as an incomplete block because the patient was able to feel pin-prick sensation, but was not able to move fingers and ankle. It was managed with sedation and analgesia by Injection Midazolam 0.02 mg/kg IV+ Injection Fentanyl 2 microgm/kg IV. General anaesthesia was not required.

- Except one, all the patients graded the experience as being very satisfied with the anaesthetic technique.

Discussion

Recently, ultrasound imaging has gained popularity in regional anaesthesia due to enhanced visibility of peripheral nerves during nerve block, reduced duration of the procedure, faster complete sensory and motors block, reduced volume of needed drugs for successful block, and decreased incidence of complications or side effects.

The popliteal nerve block is a form of regional anaesthesia utilized for a variety of foot and ankle surgeries has become a popular technique to decrease postoperative pain, decrease narcotic use, and increase patient satisfaction. Furthermore, a publication by Hegewald et al. (2014) has demonstrated

that not only is the popliteal block highly efficacious, but can also be executed by the novice foot and ankle surgeon.

We studied 40 patients who were undergoing various ankle and foot surgeries and administered ultrasonography guided popliteal nerve blocks. We monitored them closely and analyzed the data obtained.

Conclusion

Ultrasound-guided popliteal fossa nerve block is an effective and successful technique to provide peri-operative sensory and motor blockade for patients undergoing various foot and ankle surgeries. Complications associated with spinal, epidural and general anaesthesia can be avoided. Combinations of Lignocaine and Bupivacaine as a local anaesthetic provide faster onset with virtue of good postoperative analgesia. US-guided popliteal fossa nerve block has higher success rate, good haemodynamic stability, minimum complications, good satisfaction of the patients and surgeons and postoperative analgesia.

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